

QIRQQIZ FORTRESS: A NEW CHAPTER IN CENTRAL ASIAN ARCHITECTURE AND CULTURE

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Abstract: *This article is dedicated to the study of the historical and architectural significance of the Qirqqiz Fortress. By analyzing various scientific perspectives and opinions about the fortress, the research attempts to define its original purpose and social importance. The article explores the architectural structure of the fortress, its function as a scientific center, and its contribution to the development of science and culture in Central Asia. The study also focuses on the architectural style of the fortress, specifically its layout, materials, and functional aspects. The paper presents new scientific data and sources to deepen the understanding of the Qirqqiz Fortress and its historical significance.*

Keywords: *caravanserai, pavilion, monument, khanqah, dome, fortress, arch, citadel.*

INTRODUCTION

The Qirqqiz Fortress is located in the Termiz district of the Surkhandarya region and has survived to the present day in ruins. Its original function—whether it was a fortress, palace, khanqah, or caravanserai—remains uncertain, leading to various scientific interpretations. The fortress may have served as a center for learning, with medicine being one of the most important subjects taught there. Its high architectural value has contributed to its recognition as a scientific hub. This fortress, with its construction style and composition, served not only as a military structure but also as an important social and cultural center of its time.

MAIN SECTION

The Qirqqiz Fortress, dating back to the 9th–10th centuries, is located in the Termiz district of the Surxondaryo region and has remained in a ruined state until today. The original purpose of the structure—whether it was a fortress, palace, khanqah, or caravanserai—remains unclear, leading to a variety of scholarly interpretations. This article is dedicated to exploring these issues and determining the historical significance of the Qirqqiz monument.

One of the more intriguing and debated ideas is that the Qirqqiz Fortress functioned as the "Qirqqiz Academy," where the most knowledgeable girls from across Asia gathered, contributing significantly to the development of science and knowledge.

According to sources, the architectural layout of the Qirqqiz Fortress is notable for its distinctive features. The girls who lived there were provided with all the necessary conditions to acquire both secular and religious knowledge, as well as to observe the cosmos. This architectural excellence is seen as evidence that the fortress may have served as a center for scientific study.

Since 2004, the "Qirqqiz" charity and cultural-educational center in the Surxondaryo region has been contributing to the study of the fortress and its history. Among the unique manuscripts stored in the center's collection is a translated version of the work "Ilm un-Nujum," which contains a chapter dedicated to the Qirqqiz Fortress. This chapter mentions that girls from forty different countries came to the academy, passed forty exams, and were admitted. The work also states that this academy was known as a "Dar al-Funun" (a place of higher learning) and that the girls were educated in forty different scientific fields.

According to historical sources, the academy was led by Ruhaydai Davron, the daughter of Al-Hakim at-Termizi. The girls not only mastered deep knowledge but also became proficient in forty languages. Notably, the fields of medicine and astronomy were of special importance. This perspective presents the Qirqqiz Fortress not just as an architectural monument but as a significant center for the development of science.

Oral traditions describe the Qirqqiz Fortress as the residence of the heroic girl Guloyim and her forty companions, who are remembered in folklore for repelling enemy attacks with courage and valor. This legend adds a layer of cultural significance to the fortress.

Furthermore, it is noted that the Qirqqiz Fortress was known as "Shahri Somon" up until the 20th century, which indicates its prominence not only among the local population but also in terms of its historical and cultural importance.

The fortress was located outside the city of Termiz during the Middle Ages and served as a bastion, protecting the city. The fortress was constructed according to a strict plan aligned with the four cardinal directions, reflecting its military and strategic significance.

Figure 2. Qirqqiz fortress general view. (U.Nazarov).

The architectural solution of the Qirqqiz fortress is characterized by a unique layout, with arcades and corridors dividing the building into four sections. These sections include:

1. **North-western and north-eastern sections:** These parts have an identical design, each consisting of five rooms surrounded on three sides by a corridor, 2.1 meters wide.
2. **South-western section:** This section contains five rooms, interconnected by two small corridors.
3. **South-eastern section:** This area includes two rooms and a large guest hall with three columns, connected by a corridor.

All corridors and rooms are illuminated by natural light through openings in the walls, aligning with the functional and ecological principles of the architecture of the period.

The roof of the fortress features special architectural solutions, including vaulted (arched or cross-shaped) and intersecting dome-like ceilings. Domes, vaults, and arches were widely used, not only for functional purposes but also to add aesthetic beauty to the building.

Figure 3. Qirqqiz fortress top view. (U.Nazarov).

The Arab conquest led to the establishment of a need for public buildings due to the lack of such structures among the conquered peoples, prompting Arabs to build homes and facilities for their needs. In this context, Arabs were inclined to adopt architectural styles based on the palaces of the Sassanids.

A prominent example of this is the Kasr al-Xayr ash-Sharki caravanserai, built between 728–729 in Syria for Hisham ibn Abd al-Malik. This monument is distinguished by its external walls, inner courtyard, colonnaded arcade, and numerous two-story rooms. The building incorporated architectural solutions tailored to the functional needs of the Arabs.

The Kasr al-Xayr ash-Sharki was constructed under the influence of Sassanid architecture and functioned as a caravanserai. Its territory included 850 hectares of agricultural land, surrounded by a 22-kilometer-long mud brick wall. This structure not only served as an important commercial center but also provided protection and living conditions for its inhabitants.

Sassanid architectural traditions influenced the design of pavilions and palaces in the Islamic state, and their influence is also seen in Shahri Somon Fortress near Termiz. This structure, the Qirqqiz Pavilion, emerged in the 9th-10th centuries, and its square plan (54x54 m) and central courtyard (11.5x11.5 m) echoed traditional Sassanid and Mesopotamian architectural solutions.

In the 9th century, after the Sassanid and Samanid dynasties took control of the main territories of Bukhara and Movarounnahr, they developed their own state. During the Samanid period, architectural monuments, including the Qirqqiz Pavilion, gradually shifted from serving military functions to being adapted for residential and cultural needs.

The Qirqqiz Pavilion, based on a 54x54 meter square plan, featured courtyards interconnected by corridors. Each side of the building contained rectangular rooms, totaling around 50, many of which had a second floor. Some of these rooms were constructed with three columns.

The Kasr al-Xayr ash-Sharki and Qirqqiz architectural monuments show that Arab border fortifications were built on similar plans and typologies. However, the Qirqqiz monument did not function as a palace, mosque, or Samanid summer residence. It was built in accordance with the established architectural standards of the Caliphate, with the participation of skilled craftsmen.

The Qirqqiz domes mark a significant step in the transition from mudbrick architecture to brick construction, representing a new phase in Islamic architecture. This monument, located on the other side of the Amu Darya in Abbasid territory, served as a fortification, functioning as a boundary defense structure for the Arabs.

The shrinking of agricultural land in the 9th-10th centuries, coupled with the expansion of pastoralism around cities, led to the conversion of pavilions into residences and social spaces. The emergence of large feudal cities in the 11th-12th centuries continued this trend, with pavilions like the Qirqqiz remaining as private homes for feudal lords. Such monuments laid the foundation for the development of feudal architecture and urban planning in Central Asia.

CONCLUSION

The Qirqqiz Fortress, as a 9th–10th century architectural monument, occupies a unique place in the history of Central Asia. Its architectural style and structure are primarily based on the architectural traditions influenced by the Sassanid and Abbasid periods. The primary function of the fortress was related to defense and security, serving as a crucial regional defense center of its time.

Additionally, the fortress functioned as a center of knowledge and culture, not only making it an architectural monument but also contributing significantly to the intellectual heritage of Central Asia. The scholarly perspectives and architectural characteristics of the Qirqqiz Fortress provide new insights into its role and historical significance, deepening our understanding of its cultural and historical impact.

REFERENCES

1. Пугаченкова Г.А. *Очиқ осмон остидаги музей*. Т.: 1981
2. Аскарлов Ш.Дж. *Генезис архитектуры Узбекистана*. Т.: 2014
3. Назаров У.О. *Қирққиз ёдгорлиги вазифаси хақида*. Меъморчилик ва қурилиш муаммолари. Илмий-техник журнал. Самарқанд 4/2017 й.
4. Назаров У.О. *Сурхондарё шаҳарсозлиги ва меъморлиги*. Т.: 2024.
5. Sultonova D.N. *Harmony Of Art In Architecture Of Uzbekistan / Garmoniya iskusstva v arxitekture Uzbekistana* Harmony Of Art In Architecture Of Uzbekistan / Garmoniya iskusstva v arxitekture Uzbekistana.
6. www.tashkent.uz